

Advance Journal of Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences

Adv. J. Arts. Hum. & Soc Sci.

Volume: 8; Issue: 04

July-August, 2025

ISSN 6300-5290

E-ISSN 4226-6348

Impact Factor: 6.79

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/ajahss/index.php/ajahss/index>

LEADERSHIP RECRUITMENT PROCESS AND GOVERNANCE CHALLENGE IN NIGERIA

¹Popoola Michael Akin and ²Arije Olaniyi Ezekiel

¹Department of History and International Studies, Babcock University, Ilishan-Remo, Ogun State, Nigeria

²Legal Unit, Babcock University, Ilishan-Remo, Ogun State, Nigeria

E-mail: popoolam@babcock.edu.ng, arijeo@babcock.edu.ng

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20327342>

Keywords,
Democracy,
Election,
Economic
development,
Good
governance,
Leadership,
Recruitment
Process,
Undemocratic
practices.

Abstract: Multiparty democracy clearly defines the process through which political leaders could emerge. A due adherence to the process in any nation would give room for the emergence of credible and visionary leadership who would appreciate the import of good governance and properly harness the country's resources in order to translate them to wealth for the nation. The vast natural resources and adequate manpower which Nigeria is endowed with have not translated to prosperity of the citizenry. The masses have always had to grapple with extreme poverty and hunger, coupled with other palpable indices of underdevelopment. This contradiction portends governance challenge in the country. The main objective of this research is to analyse the nexus between leadership recruitment process and governance challenge in Nigeria. The research discovers that the leadership recruitment process in Nigeria is often fraught with sectional bias and other undemocratic principles which almost always lead to the emergence of deficient leadership and bad managers of government resources, resulting in the consigning of the masses into the position of unending socio-economic squalor. The paper also finds that the electorates are culpable in the warped recruitment process which leads to the bad governance which they experience. It recommends that the masses should use the franchise power conferred on them by the constitution with discretion in their own interest. Qualitative research methodology was adopted in the study.

Introduction.

Nigeria is a country located in the Gulf of Guinea with a total area of 923,768km². The United

Popoola Michael Akin and Arije Olaniyi Ezekiel

Advance Journal of Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences

Adv. J. Arts. Hum. & Soc Sci.

Volume: 8; Issue: 04

July-August, 2025

ISSN 6300-5290

E-ISSN 4226-6348

Impact Factor: 6.79

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/ajahss/index.php/ajahss/index>

Nation's data as estimated by Worldometer, put the country's population at 235 million inhabitants in January 2024 (Adewole, 2024). The nation is considered the world 20th largest economy and the largest economy in Africa. The World Economics estimates the 2025 GDP of the nation at \$2.593 trillion (World Economics, 2025). In addition, with a coastline of about 853 kilometers, the country is endowed with abundance of natural gas and petroleum. It has about 159 oil fields and 1,480 oil wells (Chukwu, 2025) This made the nation the leading oil exporter in Africa and the sixth leading oil exporter in the world. Other natural resources which the nation has in abundance include: bitumen, iron ore, coal, tin, lime stone, zinc, and lead. Aside this, the country is also blessed with arable land and good climate which support copious growth of both food and cash crops. To crown it all, the nation has the third largest youth population in the world, ranking after India and China. Over 55 per cent of the country's population is made up of young people of below 18 years (UNDP, 2024). The implication of this is that the nation should, on a regular basis, have a steady labour force with which to harness its abundant resources.

Under normal circumstances, the superfluous availability of human and natural resources, as described above, should make the country a safe and comfortable haven for its citizens and a desired country of destination for foreigners from other nations of the world. Paradoxically

however, Nigeria remains one of the poorest countries in the world. In its 2024 Nigeria Development Update (NDU), the World Bank claimed that the Nigerians living below poverty line rose from 40.1% in 2018 to 50% in 2024 (Olayinka and Chibueze, 2024). The report also indicated that Nigeria had become the nation with the most extreme poor people in the world. In addition, Nigeria is beleaguered with indices of bad governance such as insecurity, poor health care, prevalence of preventable diseases, deplorable public infrastructure, parlous educational sector, huge external debt, net capital flight, ethno-religious crisis, corruption, unemployment, underemployment, poor purchasing power, inflation, low standard of living and a host of others. All these leave the average man on the street with nothing but poverty, anger, stress, hopelessness, haplessness and helplessness. Regrettably, the situation still remains the same as at the time of conducting this research in 2025.

From the foregoing, it is very clear that the leadership of the country has not been able to harness the abundant resources of the country in a way that would make wealth and prosperity available to all. Before any nation could grow economically, socially and politically, it must have leadership that can choose its onions appropriately, leadership that has a clear cut vision of what governance means and who can make the interest and welfare of the citizenry a priority. This is why the concept of good

Popoola Michael Akin and Arije Olaniyi Ezekiel

Advance Journal of Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences

Adv. J. Arts. Hum. & Soc Sci.

Volume: 8; Issue: 04

July-August, 2025

ISSN 6300-5290

E-ISSN 4226-6348

Impact Factor: 6.79

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/ajahss/index.php/ajahss/index>

leadership and the pivotal role which it plays in ensuring socio-political and economic well-being of a nation has continued to gain wider currency in the contemporary discourse.

Meanwhile, the emergence of good leadership does not just happen by accident. In constitutional democracy, there are some basic tenets and condition which are supposed to drive the recruitment or emergence of credible leadership. Some of these principles are ; adherence to the rule of law, availability of strong and well organized political parties, democratic selection of party candidates, robust inter-party competition, impartial electoral umpire, free, fair and credible election, independent judiciary, neutral law enforcement agencies among others. Any compromise of the process would inadvertently lead to the emergence of wrong leaders without the requisite experience to handle the machinery of government, not to talk of delivering the dividend of democracy to the people. This study therefore set out to examine the conditions that characterise leadership recruitment process in Nigeria and the effect of that on governance in the country. The gap which the paper fills is taking a decoy from the usual norm of heaping the blame of bad governance in Nigeria solely on the leadership. The followership (electorates) who play active role in the recruitment of leadership is also a common feature in the process. The idea of always blaming the leadership and ignoring the ever influential characteristic nature of the followership is one of

the major problems militating against Nigeria's progress

Literature review of Concept of Leadership

From the early Greek era to modern period, the issue of leadership has occupied a strategic position in people's quest for socio-political, economic and religious development. Liden et al, (2025) describe leadership as a social influence process in which leaders attempt to organize, motivate and enable followers to contribute toward achieving collective goal of the society. This perspective implies that leadership involves giving directions to citizens who are a critical asset to any country whether developed or underdeveloped. To corroborate this, the Havard Business School (2025) opines that one of the concrete skills that set real leaders apart is the ability to influence the followers to appreciate the weakness and strength of the organization, guide them towards seeing the bigger picture and direct them towards achieving success. Gleeson's emphasis is on transformational and purpose – driven leadership. To him, a purpose driven leader is the one who prioritize values, ethics, and social responsibility and also engage, stimulate or inspire followers to achieve extraordinary outcomes (Gleeson, 2024). He highlights the significance of a clear and meaningful mission beyond selfish and parochial interest in order to drive the followers towards contributing to a better societal goods. Haslam et al (2024) observed that leadership is not a solo process but

Popoola Michael Akin and Arije Olaniyi Ezekiel

Advance Journal of Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences

Adv. J. Arts. Hum. & Soc Sci.

Volume: 8; Issue: 04

July-August, 2025

ISSN 6300-5290

E-ISSN 4226-6348

Impact Factor: 6.79

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/ajahss/index.php/ajahss/index>

one that is firmly rooted in relationships and connections between leaders and those that they lead. They opined that it is only a zombie leadership that will focus attention on himself and undermine the importance of followers, relationships and collectivity. To them, without followership, there cannot be leadership.

All these imply that leadership is the ability of the person given the position of leadership to inspire, direct, motivate and encourage the people being led to work together and harmoniously in the quest for the achievement of group goals. The group could be the entire country, or part thereof. Hence, leadership can be seen as both the bonding agent that binds members of a group together as well as the spur that triggers off their motivation in order to enable them have a major influence on their performance. Although, the followers may not always see things from the perspectives of the leaders. But the ability of the leader to provide appropriate and adequate guidance and direction to the members of the society is what would help the leader to achieve cohesion and coherence which will be needed to harness the associated efforts for the ultimate achievements of common goals without the deployment coercion.

One crucial thing that stands out the concept of leadership which the above definitions failed to mention is the notion of trust. Trust is what could help the leader to influence the feelings, belief, behaviors and actions of the followers towards the achievement of the set goals. Trust is what will

convince the followers that the goals set by the leadership are for the common benefit of the society. Trust is what will inspire the people to make a total, willing and voluntary commitment towards accomplishing or even exceeding societal or organizational goals. Hence leadership is meant to be a bundle of attributes or a reflection of characteristics or qualities which include, but may not be limited to knowledge, vision, courage, openness, accountability, determination, transparency, uprightness and competence which will create an environment of mutual trust between the leadership and the people being led.

Political Leadership

Political leadership is a complex concept with no universally accepted definition. Political scientists usually define political leadership based on their individual perceptions of the issue and particularly, the aspects they are more interested in. Political leadership could refer to a group of people that have been entrusted with the state power and which can be seen as a major determinant of the nature, form, character and process of government and governance across the world (Ekundayo, 2016). According to Filipet 2012, political leadership is conceived as an essential feature of all government and governance. Good leadership secures the welfare and prosperity of the citizenry. Hence, credible, legitimate and strong leadership are sine qua non to good governance and the success of the government. On the contrary, the emergence of incredible, weak and fool hardy leadership may

Popoola Michael Akin and Arije Olaniyi Ezekiel

Advance Journal of Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences

Adv. J. Arts. Hum. & Soc Sci.

Volume: 8; Issue: 04

July-August, 2025

ISSN 6300-5290

E-ISSN 4226-6348

Impact Factor: 6.79

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/ajahss/index.php/ajahss/index>

lead to bad governance and may even bring about catastrophe in governance.

Political leadership is meant to interpret the societal problems and prescribe means to solve them. It is expected to create and propagate visions as solutions or responses to problems, inspire people, mobilize followers to believe in their vision, accept their diagnosis of, and policy prescriptions for societal and collective problems or tasks (Nye, 2008). When we talk about political leadership, it must be understood purely in the context of its capacity to resolve problems and lead the people to their destined goal and national objective. Abdurafiu, (2020) point out that political leadership overlaps with other forms or types of social leadership because leadership generally, whether social or political is related to power or has some elements of power no matter how little. However, it is said that political leadership is premised on a unique set of power relations between the leader and his followers and that is why it is said to be stronger and more important than any other type of social leadership. The reason for this is that political leadership has a monopolistic or preferred access to the deployment of coercive and inducing hard power in addition to attracting, persuasive soft power based on ideology. Therefore, political leadership can be defined as a unique set of power relations and influences that is exercised over a broad range of salient issues covering foreign affairs, defense, social well-being among others, nationally and globally, and from a position of

authoritative preponderance involving ideologies and ethics (Masciulli et al 2009)

While drawing the correlation between political leadership and followership, Ekundayo (2016) posits that in order to understand, explain and predict the nature and pattern of political leadership, followership also needs to be considered because one begets the other. Political leadership does not exist in a vacuum. Both leaders and followers are involved in a transactional or transformational relationship. Therefore, they both influence each other.

The Necessary Conditions for Leadership Recruitment

This study conceives political leadership recruitment process as the necessary systematic conditions which guarantee the emergence of credible political leaders in position of power and authority either by selection or election, conducted in a free and fair atmosphere. One of the uniqueness of constitutional democracy is that it stipulates the process through which leadership could emerge as well as some guiding principles which must be applied in order to ensure strict compliance with the process. Some of the processes are:- strong and well-organized political parties and party systems, well defined system of selecting party candidates, robust inter-party competition and relations, Universal adult suffrage, effective and efficient security services, effective and efficient media coverage and election monitoring, credibility and acceptability of the election results, an independent judiciary as

Popoola Michael Akin and Arije Olaniyi Ezekiel

Advance Journal of Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences

Adv. J. Arts. Hum. & Soc Sci.

Volume: 8; Issue: 04

July-August, 2025

ISSN 6300-5290

E-ISSN 4226-6348

Impact Factor: 6.79

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/ajahss/index.php/ajahss/index>

well as appropriate punitive measure for electoral offenders.

Ekundayo (2016) emphasizes that the above mentioned parameters are necessary conditions that must be put in place in any society before it could be referred to as a democracy. They are also the conditions that must be fulfilled in order to ensure free, fair and credible process of leadership recruitment.

The above position reinforces Idada & Uhunmwuango's view which states that democracy as well as democratic mode of leadership recruitment can only thrive under certain known conditions. It is only in the societies where such conditions are obtainable that we can have the emergence of credible political leaders who know their onions. They opine further that one can talk of thriving democracy only in any political community:-

“Where people freely stand for elections and vote during elections based on universal adult suffrage; where the conduct of elections are free, fair and credible; where the process of election is competitive among the political parties; where defeated leaders accept defeat freely after elections; where political leadership succession process is smooth and not problematic; where freedom of speech, publication and association is allowed; where the government and its agents adhere to the rule of law; where the rule of majority is maintained and where there is acceptance of opposing views (Idada & Uhunmwuango, 2012)”.

Political leadership recruitment would be made easy, simple and smooth only in a society where the above tenets, elements or parameters exist simply because the process would be in tandem with the dictate of democracy.

Some of the tenets are discussed below:

Strong and Well-organized Political Parties and Party Systems:

Democratic system necessitates the establishment of strong and highly competitive political parties as well as a strong and well-organized party systems which exist in different forms or varieties such as; one-party, two-party and multi-party systems. (Although, the ideal party system in liberal democracy is two-party or multi-party system). Political parties are organizations that nominate or present candidates to stand for elections in their names and seek to have or place representatives or leaders in government. Their primary objectives are to; organize themselves, dominate the organs of government and ultimately provide governmental and political leadership. Political parties can also be viewed as political groups whose members act in concert to win support for leaders who seek to govern (Jinadu, 2011). This condition serves as the beginning of credible leadership recruitment process in a democratic society.

Democratic Selection of Party Candidates:

Another parameter that could guarantee the recruitment of dependable people into leadership position is democratic selection of credible party

Advance Journal of Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences

Adv. J. Arts. Hum. & Soc Sci.

Volume: 8; Issue: 04

July-August, 2025

ISSN 6300-5290

E-ISSN 4226-6348

Impact Factor: 6.79

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/ajahss/index.php/ajahss/index>

candidates. This is one of the major functions of a political party. This can be possible if political parties give room for internal democracy which is sine-qua non to a robust intra-party competition. Democratic selection of party candidates can forestall Godfatherism, imposition of candidates, monetization and manipulation of the political leadership process.

According to Hopkin & Bradbury (2006), some of the methods through which political party select candidates to represent them in elections include apparent consensus or formal voting during party annual convention or conference. It may also be done through party delegate primaries at various levels from ward, local government, state and federal or national level. Whichever method is adopted in selecting the right candidate to represent the party, open and due process must be followed otherwise, a wrong candidate would emerge as the flag bearer of the party and this may result in bad governance.

Robust Inter-Party Competition and Relation:

Another important parameter in political leadership recruitment is a healthy inter-party relationship. This refers to how the political parties relate to one another in terms of achieving co-operation and consensus or as regards conflict management. A healthy inter-party competition and relations are very key to successful leadership recruitment process. Where these are in existence, the various political parties will have a common understanding and be willing to easily

concede defeat to one another after election. Conversely, where it is lacking, political parties would resort to dubious and fraudulent means of winning elections either by hook or crook. This could also lead to intense inter-party conflicts, crises and violence and eventually bring about the emergence of wrong leaders (Dode, 2010).

Universal Adult Suffrage:

Democracy thrives where people can freely contest for election and also cast their votes based on universal adult suffrage. Elections are the crucial instruments of recruiting political leaders by the electorate, under the close watch of an impartial electoral management agency. Through a free and fair election, the masses have the political right to decide who should govern them. It enables them to have a say in the governance of their country through their elected leaders and representatives. It gives them the opportunity of rejecting or accepting the people that rule over them. Hence, free and fair election has been described as a mechanism which oil the democratic process. It is the only credible parameter which allows for political leadership recruitment, succession and change in a democracy. In other words, democracy is all about establishing political parties, nurturing party systems, conducting elections and choosing political leaders through universal adult suffrage (Diamond, 2002; Luqman, 2009).

Impartial Electoral Umpire

The agency that is responsible for the conduct of election is essential to the success of the political

Advance Journal of Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences

Adv. J. Arts. Hum. & Soc Sci.

Volume: 8; Issue: 04

July-August, 2025

ISSN 6300-5290

E-ISSN 4226-6348

Impact Factor: 6.79

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/ajahss/index.php/ajahss/index>

leadership recruitment or electoral process. The quality and credibility of elections and ultimately the success of the political leadership recruitment process can be greatly impacted by the competency of the electoral institution (Edigheji, 2006; Yaqub, 2006). It is expected that the electoral body is truly independent, transparent and impartial in the performance of its function as stipulated by the law, particularly as it affects political leadership recruitment. The electoral umpire must be seen or perceived in reality by all the actors in the political leadership recruitment process to be neutral, objective and impartial. The electoral umpire should also be able to live above board in the area of implementing the electoral laws, such as the law that regulates the activities of all political parties, the conduct of their members and candidates, as well as the limited amount which an aspirant could spend during political campaign. Without a vibrant, competent and strong electoral body which could put the necessary check in place, political parties would flout electoral laws with impunity. Consequently, this could compromise political leadership recruitment process and give room to the ascendancy of incredible leaders. **Effective and Efficient Security Services:**

In other to enforce and maintain law and order in the society and make election free and fair, there must be effective and efficient security service in the country. It is the duty of the security agencies to ensure that every actor in the electoral process complies with the electoral laws so as to avoid

rigging, violence, malpractices and other manipulations in the leadership recruitment exercise. It is not only the electoral umpire that should be non-partisan, the security agencies too need to be impartial. A compromised security agency may look the other way when electoral laws are being flagrantly violated and this will certainly lead to a humongous flaw in the recruitment process.

Effective and Efficient Media Coverage and Election Monitoring:

Important stakeholders such as the media, civil societies, and election observation and monitoring groups (local and international) constitute an important parameter for free and fair election. The roles of the media and civil society organisations in the electoral process commence with intensive political enlightenment and civic education of the masses to encourage them to shun political apathy, exercise their franchise, avoid selling their votes and distance themselves from the evils of election rigging (Luqman, 2009).

Election monitoring by local and international observers, are also very crucial to the emergence of credible leadership because their presence and unbiased performance of their functions would add credence to the electoral process as well as election result. Their role is particularly essential where the power of incumbency can be abused by the ruling party. (Okoye, 2007).

Wide Acceptability of the Election Results:

Popoola Michael Akin and Arije Olaniyi Ezekiel

Advance Journal of Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences

Adv. J. Arts. Hum. & Soc Sci.

Volume: 8; Issue: 04

July-August, 2025

ISSN 6300-5290

E-ISSN 4226-6348

Impact Factor: 6.79

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/ajahss/index.php/ajahss/index>

Election results must not only be credible, it must also be acceptable to the generality of the major actors in the electoral process; that is, the electorates, the political parties and even the defeated candidates (Ekundayo, 2016). However, before the result of an election can be acceptable to all the stake holders, the process leading to the election must be seen by all to have passed credibility and acceptability test. A faulty, skewed or manipulated electoral process cannot produce an acceptable result because it would unavoidably lead to the emergence of a wrong candidate.

Independent Judiciary:

For the judiciary to perform its constitutional roles, particularly on adjudicating electoral matters, it must be truly independent and transparent. It must also be courageous enough to adjudicate on dispute arising from electoral malpractices impartially, speedily and without fear or favour. An impartial judiciary will elicit the confidence of the stake holders in the electoral process because they would be confident of getting redress in the court whenever any unfairness is perceived.

Due Prosecution of Electoral Offenders.

As a corollary to the last point mentioned above, a reliable leadership recruitment process includes the availability and strict application of a strong law which stipulates the process of dishing out punitive measures to electoral offenders. In every developed democracy, the electoral laws are not only sophisticated, adequate and non-restrictive, they are also being reviewed periodically,

amended, made free from ambiguity and easily adjudicated upon. It is a known fact that electoral malpractices thrive where there is no punitive measures to electoral offenders. It is very natural for human beings to throw caution to the wind and embark on reckless violation of the law if there is no expectation of sanction or some form of disciplinary measure.

Leadership Recruitment Process in Nigeria

All the parameters highlighted above are clearly spelt out in the Nigeria electoral act which serves as the compass of political leadership recruitment process. Unfortunately, the process of recruiting political leadership in the country is fraught with all kinds of considerations and practices which are antithetical to these tenets. This often leads to the emergence of wrong leaders who lack the ability to manage the wealth of the country appropriately. The issues that influence leadership recruitment process in Nigeria are discussed below:-

Zoning Formula

One of the aberrations which often compromise the emergence of credible candidates in Nigeria's electoral process is what is popularly referred to as 'zoning formula'. This happens when a political party decides to limit those who can contest for a particular political position to a certain section of the country or state or senatorial district as the case may be. The implication of this is that those who are not from that zone would be excluded from vying for that particular position either during primary or final elections, regardless of their competence or capability. This, in most cases, sacrifices merit and leads to the emergence

Popoola Michael Akin and Arije Olaniyi Ezekiel

Advance Journal of Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences

Adv. J. Arts. Hum. & Soc Sci.

Volume: 8; Issue: 04

July-August, 2025

ISSN 6300-5290

E-ISSN 4226-6348

Impact Factor: 6.79

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/ajahss/index.php/ajahss/index>

of mediocre who do not have the competence to govern. A political leader who lacks the requisite ability to govern cannot deliver the dividend of democracy to the people.

Closely related to the above point is the issue of 'Consensus candidate' which is also a popular way of recruiting party flag bearer in Nigeria. Consensus takes place when a political party claims that it has taken a joint decision to choose a particular candidate out of the several candidates that are willing to present themselves for primary election for a particular position. Whenever a party has a consensus candidate for an elective position, primary election will not be conducted for that position. In most cases, the consensus decision is based on ethnic chauvinism, religious bigotry, group prejudice, gender sexism, among others. Hence, religion, group or ethnic affiliation serves as rallying points during electoral process. Most often than not, what is referred to as consensus is often the decision of a few powerful and influential members of the party to the exclusion of the majority of the party members. This process also compromises merit and leads to the emergence of incompetent people at the corridor of power. Wherever this kind parochial sentiment is allowed to hold sway, good governance would be the casualty and that has been the situation in Nigeria.

Moneybags.

The political space in Nigeria is often hijacked by the rich party members who are referred to as

'Money-bags'. They buy the electoral process right from primary election up to the final election. They spend money to secure the favour of the general voting populace by distributing items such as rice, salt, motor bike, telephone handsets, vests, fez cap, airtime vouchers, sewing machines, cutlasses and other farm imputes such as fertilizer. To crown it all, money is freely distributed either on the eve of election or on the day of Election, sometimes, in the presence of security officers who are meant to curb such acts. Vote buying was carried to a brazen level during the gubernatorial elections in Ekiti and Osun states in 2022 as well as the 2023 general elections as the social media was inundated with pictures of the electorates who barefacedly displayed the money which they collected from the politician (Nwachukwu, 2022, Ezediumo, 2023). The popular phraseology in the western region of the country now is "*Dibo ki o sebe*" which is literally interpreted as 'cast your vote and prepare a sumptuous pot of soup'. The moneybags often cash-in on the prevailing poverty level in Nigeria to perpetrate this atrocity. Thus, the common trend in Nigeria is that elections are won by only those who have huge amount of money to spend during election while those who don't have enough money to spend fall by the way side, irrespective of the political sagacity or administrative acumen they might possess. This informs the popular saying that 'election is for the highest bidder' in Nigeria.

It is common knowledge that the two major

Popoola Michael Akin and Arije Olaniyi Ezekiel

Advance Journal of Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences

Adv. J. Arts. Hum. & Soc Sci.

Volume: 8; Issue: 04

July-August, 2025

ISSN 6300-5290

E-ISSN 4226-6348

Impact Factor: 6.79

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/ajahss/index.php/ajahss/index>

political parties in Nigeria, which are, the All Progressive Congress (APC) and the People's Democratic Party (PDP) spend huge amount of money to buy votes during election. When one hears members of the two political parties accusing each other of monetizing an election, it is because the party being accused has succeeded in doling out more cash in vote buying and thereby securing more votes in a particular area or state than the accuser. Hence, the situation is not that one party was giving out cash to the electorates while the other one is trying to tow the path of integrity. The electorates too, who consider doling out of cash by political parties as the unwritten rule of the game, are always expectant of this aberration. Otherwise, the election may record a very low turnout.

Although, the Nigerian Electoral Act contains a provision which stipulates the maximum amount of money which a candidate vying for a particular position could spend. The essence of this is to prevent money-bags from hijacking the process and to create a plain field for all contestants (both the rich and the poor). However, the Independent National Electoral Commission which serves as the guardian of the law pays little attention to this aspect of the electoral act either due to sheer neglect or because it does not possess the mechanism to determine how much a candidate spends. This also results in incompetent people winning elections and ruling the people

God-Fatherism

This is another popular parlance in the political

lexicon of Nigeria. It implies that a politician vying for a position must receive the blessing and strong backing of a party stalwart who is referred to as a 'god father'. The so called god fathers are the influential people in the society who can use their political clout, popularity, money, propaganda and ability to attract followers to their political son and if necessary, unleash violence on political opponents, to help their god son to win an election. Hence, god-fatherism in the contemporary Nigerian politics involves the use of propaganda, blackmail, thuggery, hooliganism, kidnapping, issuing of threats, political assassinations, all forms of criminality, malevolence, oppression, selfishness, self-serving and parasitism.

While the god-father is doing all these for the god-son, the god-son on his own part would be made to pledge his unalloyed loyalty to the god-father. In some cases, an oath of allegiance is taken by the god son to assure the god father that he would ever remain loyal to him and would always carry out his bid if the election is won by him. Not unexpectedly, when the god-son assumes political position, his loyalty would be to the god-father rather than the electorates. In this kind of scenario, consideration for merit or competence during leadership recruitment is sacrificed for allegiance of loyalty to the godfather. This, undoubtedly, is one of the reasons Nigeria has been a bastion of bad leadership

Influence of Crowd

Popoola Michael Akin and Arije Olaniyi Ezekiel

Advance Journal of Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences

Adv. J. Arts. Hum. & Soc Sci.

Volume: 8; Issue: 04

July-August, 2025

ISSN 6300-5290

E-ISSN 4226-6348

Impact Factor: 6.79

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/ajahss/index.php/ajahss/index>

Another intriguing fact about Nigerian electorates is that they are easily influenced by the crowd in choosing who to vote for. During electioneering campaigns, the credibility of a candidate is gauged by the massive crowd at his campaign rally. This easily sways the ambivalent electorates to decide the candidate who will get their votes. The politicians understand this mentality and that is why some of them go to the extent of renting crowds or paying people to attend their campaign rally all in a bid to give the masses the impression that they are more popular than their co-contenders. This too, often lead to the election of incompetent candidate into government office.

Election Malpractice

Free, fair and credible election is undoubtedly the foundation upon which democracy rest. Hence, it is a major tool for leadership recruitment. Regrettably, election in Nigeria has always been fraught with all forms of malpractices and this has often impacted the emergence of political leaders in a negative way. A study of the annals of Nigeria political history since independence would reveal that the successive elections in the country have been devoid of essential ingredients of fair democratic contest. Desperate politicians always adopt different kinds of electoral malpractices such as buying of voters card, ballot stuffing, snatching of ballot boxes, illegal printing of voters' card; illegal thumb-printing of ballot papers, under-age voting and falsification of election results, shockingly, with the connivance of the opposition parties agents.

Other forms of electoral malpractices include compilation of fictitious names of voters' list; illegal printing and use of forms used for election results; deliberate refusal to supply election materials to certain areas; announcing of election results in places where no elections were held; unauthorized announcement of election results; harassment of candidates, agents and voters; change of list of electoral officials without due process; illegal arrest and detention of political opponents on the eve of election, and sporadic shooting in the air by political thugs at polling centers to scare away voters (Ibrahim, 2007), Consequently, every general election held in the country, particularly since 1965, has been a subject of contestation and characterized by post-election violence of varying degree. This is why Lamidi et al (2014) described election in Nigeria as constant tales of violence, fraud and manipulation.

It has been stated above that the existence of impartial security agency is very crucial to leadership recruitment process. But in Nigeria, the security agencies are sometimes found as pawns in the hands of the ruling party in a particular area. Most of the acts of malpractices stated above take place in the glare of the security agencies while they keep mute or feign ignorance of what is happening. Sometimes they are even used by the ruling/dominating party in an area to harass members of the opposition party. This became very pronounced during the 2003 and 2007 general elections when the incumbent

Popoola Michael Akin and Arije Olaniyi Ezekiel

Advance Journal of Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences

Adv. J. Arts. Hum. & Soc Sci.

Volume: 8; Issue: 04

July-August, 2025

ISSN 6300-5290

E-ISSN 4226-6348

Impact Factor: 6.79

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/ajahss/index.php/ajahss/index>

President then, Chief Olusegun Obasanjo espoused that the elections for him and his political party (PDP) were a matter of “a do or die” affair (Adejumobi, 2007). Any recruitment process that runs this way would certainly not engender the election of competent leaders who can guarantee good governance

Complicity of the Electoral Umpire

The Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) which serves as the electoral umpire in Nigeria is often accused of betraying its “independence and neutrality” status. In 2007, the electoral body was accused of pursuing frivolous cases against some opposition party’s candidates so as to disqualify them rather than focus on its constitutional duty (Suberu, 2007). The introduction of card reader machine by the electoral body during the 2015 general elections was hailed as a welcome idea to curb the evil of multiple voting. But the card reader machine is not without its vulnerability and this has been exploited by unscrupulous politicians, allegedly, in connivance with some corrupt INEC officials to bypass the electronic verification process in order to engage in multiple voting (Nwangwu, 2015).

Similarly, some electorates expressed their disappointment at the Electoral Commission based on the allegation that some faulty card readers were intentionally deployed to the stronghold of the opposition party (Nwangwu, 2015). In addition, INEC has been severally accused of its inability to press charges against the culprits of electoral malpractices. This has made

election malpractice to continue unabated.

Leadership Recruitment Process and Governance Challenges in Nigeria

This faulty process has been the means through which the political leadership are being recruited in Nigeria over the years. Suffice it to say too, that the undemocratic recruitment process is being carried out by the political elite. But they often use the masses or the electorates to legitimize their ignoble actions. The fact that the followership (electorates) are the main actors in the leadership recruitment process through which the political leaders get to position of authority put on the laps of the followership the right to use its mandate to decide who should stay in position of authority and who should not, by strictly insisting on following democratic tenets in the recruitment process. The followership as well as the leadership play equally important role in the type of governance which they live under. Unfortunately, rather than reiterate their importance, the Nigerian electorates undermine their value and offer their rights for sale at every stage of the process of election as they settle for the monetary inducement which the politicians offer to motivate them to cast their votes. Most of the people which this researcher interacted with in the course of writing this paper opined that they would exercise their franchise only if they are mobilized to do so through financial inducement. This popular abnormality in Nigeria is premised on the wrong notion that the money which the politicians are offering them during election time

Popoola Michael Akin and Arije Olaniyi Ezekiel

Advance Journal of Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences

Adv. J. Arts. Hum. & Soc Sci.

Volume: 8; Issue: 04

July-August, 2025

ISSN 6300-5290

E-ISSN 4226-6348

Impact Factor: 6.79

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/ajahss/index.php/ajahss/index>

is their own share of the 'National Cake'.

The business of leading a country as big and endowed as Nigeria entails formulating policies that would proffer solutions to the country's myriads of challenges and guide the country to prosperity. But this could only happen where the leadership recruitment process gives room for the emergence of a cerebral politician with astute administrative acumen who knows that occupying political leadership position is about service to the people. But where the electorates offer themselves as tools of political manipulation in the hands of the political elite, during leadership recruitment process, the end result will always be the emergence of corrupt, incompetent and clueless leadership who would not see their positions as service to the country but avenues for personal enrichment and aggrandizement. In such a situation, governance challenge, such as Nigeria has been experiencing since the First Republic would hold sway.

According to Nwagboso and Duke (2012), the civilian leadership of the nation, right from its political independence, has been bereft of the vision, the passion and the character to effectively administer the nation and deal with the decaying economy. They are only good at making promises during electioneering campaigns which they trash into the dustbin after getting the people's mandate. In other words, the promises of economic prosperity and social progress which they make during campaign fizzle away as soon as they are confirmed in office. The only thing the

masses see is a political leadership that is disorderly, unpatriotic, corrupt, self-seeking, full of mediocrity and grossly inefficient. This often lead to 'progressive retrogression' of the socio-economic sector and massive dilapidation of public infrastructures which leave the average man to keep struggling hard on a daily basis to eke out living.

While lamenting this, Chigbu (2012) posit that "Most Nigerian leaders do not cherish the ethics of good governance in their mad rush to acquire political power and wealth. Values such as truthfulness, transparency, accountability and responsibility do not make any appeal to them". Consequently, they have not only brought about weak and dysfunctional state institutions, their inability to provide effective and inspiring leadership has also bred followership that is distrustful of such leadership and mutually antagonistic of one another. No thanks to the fault process through which the leaders emerge.

The abundant resources of the nation have almost turned out to be a curse for the masses as the country is beleaguered with all the indices of bad governance such as inequality, injustice, marginalization, unemployment, high cost of living, poor standard of living, and abject poverty. The industrial sector of the country is ailing due to unfavorable industrial policies, while the power sector is epileptic, forcing people to depend on generating sets to run their businesses and power their homes. Also, the public infrastructures are dilapidating by the day due to sheer neglect and

Popoola Michael Akin and Arije Olaniyi Ezekiel

Advance Journal of Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences

Adv. J. Arts. Hum. & Soc Sci.

Volume: 8; Issue: 04

July-August, 2025

ISSN 6300-5290

E-ISSN 4226-6348

Impact Factor: 6.79

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/ajahss/index.php/ajahss/index>

lack of maintenance culture. Preventable diseases such as malaria, diarrhea, and yellow fever continue to claim a lot of lives, while air and water pollution occasioned by improper sewage disposal threatened people's lives on a daily basis. Nigerians grapple with wide spread insecurity such as cattle rustling, ethnic militancy, ethno-religious tension, terrorism, and kidnapping on a daily basis. The security situation is so traumatic that the people dread commuting from one location to the other. In addition, the agricultural sector which should have given the country a comparative advantage is not getting adequate attention from the government while the rural areas hardly feel the presence of the government. They are mostly ignored and thus, a lot of natural resources which should have increased the wealth of the country remain untapped.

Resultantly, the globally acknowledged economic potentials of Nigeria have not translated to prosperity for the citizens. Every successive administration leaves the country worse off than it met it. The only thing that is consistently on the increase in Nigeria is corruption which takes new dimension whenever a new administration assumes office. Little wonder Ukaegbu (2010) comments that; "Looking around Nigeria, nothing but colossal failure is evident. From the local government all the way to the presidency, the only business of government is the monumental and frenzied looting of the nation's coffers, while the huddled masses reek in unbelievable poverty and destitution". This is the

way the leadership of Nigeria has been running the affairs of the nation. They have run Nigeria aground to the extent that the country is almost becoming a failed state.

However, it is important to know that whenever Nigerians are complaining about the impunity of the political office holders, they should know and acknowledge the fact that their sense of impunity were given to them through the choices which the electorates make at one time or the other during the leadership recruitment process. The recruitment process cannot be compromised by the political elite without the consent of the electorates. The position of leadership is a position of service to the people. But when people 'buy' their way into the corridor of power, it's only logical that credible or visionary leadership could not be expected from them and that is the reason the nation has always been governed by ineffective, inefficient, irresponsible, unaccountable and opaque leaders.

Most political leaders in Nigeria conceive politics as investment which should yield bountiful dividend for them. This make them to appropriate the people's commonwealth to themselves while the electorates are left to wallow in misery and abject poverty as they keep complaining about lack of good governance. Regrettably, the vicious circle continues to repeat itself at all election periods. That is why Daniel opines that Nigerian masses are not serious or ready to make the sacrifice in order to get the right kind of leadership (Daniel, 2022). While evincing the

Popoola Michael Akin and Arije Olaniyi Ezekiel

Advance Journal of Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences

Adv. J. Arts. Hum. & Soc Sci.

Volume: 8; Issue: 04

July-August, 2025

ISSN 6300-5290

E-ISSN 4226-6348

Impact Factor: 6.79

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/ajahss/index.php/ajahss/index>

same view, Anyim attributes Nigeria setback to the leadership recruitment process in the nation. According to him, when the society puts the leadership who is ill equipped in the position of authority, they can only reap mediocrity and lackluster performance (Anyim, 2021).

Conclusion

No nation has ever achieved greatness or meaningful social, political and economic development without having articulate, visionary, purposeful, selfless and intellectually cerebral people in leadership position. In democracy, this type of leadership emerges through a recruitment process which is free and fair and devoid of selfish, parochial and unintelligent choice of the people. This research has proved however that this has not been Nigerian case. Nigeria has witnessed frequent development crises and stunted economic growth, resulting from bad governance over the years. The failure of the country has been adduced largely to the emergence of political opportunists who assume responsibility to govern without having a clear cut vision of any concrete plans of how to translate the abundant wealth of the country to guarantee national development. These are political leaders who get to the corridor of power through deficient and compromised leadership recruitment process.

The conclusion of this paper therefore is that for the glooming situation occasioned by bad governance to change in Nigeria, the masses which are crucial stakeholders in the leadership

recruitment process need to get their acts together and use their right and power to make choice appropriately. In democracy, power belongs to the people who take a decision to hand it over to whoever they choose to exercise the power on their behalf. Representative democracy may not necessarily guarantee good government, but the beauty of it is that it guarantees periodic change. This gives the people the opportunity to recognize that their fate is in their hands and they can exercise this right by booting out any administration that is not performing.

The paper therefore concludes that it is high time the Nigerian masses realised that their socio-economic predicament mostly spring from the wrong choices they make during electoral process. Whenever the electorates allow antidemocratic sentiments to becloud their sense of judgement during leadership recruitment process, they would have no other choice than to live with the consequence which is bad governance. The paper also recommends that the National Orientation Agency (NOA) should be alive to its responsibility of giving constant political education to the people on this matter. Moreover, civil society organisations need to engage in vigorous advocacy for the independence and strengthening of the institutions that play important roles in leadership recruitment process such as the INEC, the police and the judiciary. They also need to call these institutions to order whenever they are found wanting in the respective areas of their responsibilities.

Popoola Michael Akin and Arije Olaniyi Ezekiel

Advance Journal of Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences

Adv. J. Arts. Hum. & Soc Sci.

Volume: 8; Issue: 04

July-August, 2025

ISSN 6300-5290

E-ISSN 4226-6348

Impact Factor: 6.79

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/ajahss/index.php/ajahss/index>

References

AbduRafiu, M. (2020) "Leadership Recruitment" *The Guardian*, July 9

Adejumobi, S. (2007). *When Votes Do Not Count: The 2007 General Elections in Nigeria*. Uppsala, Sweden: The Nordic African Institute.

Adewole Segun (2024) Nigeria's Population to Cross 237Million by 2025-Report. *The Guardian*, December 31 2024.

Anyim, Pius Anyim (2021) "Leadership Recruitment, Recruitment, Causes of Nigeria's Setback. *The Punch*, October 8

Chigbu A. (2012) *The Punch Newspaper*, April, 28, page 28

Chukwu Oluchi (2025) Full List of Oil Well Owners in Nigeria. *Nigeria Queries*. <https://nigeriaqueries.com/full-list-of-oil-well-owners-in-nigeria/>

Daniel, Eniola (2022) "Our Leadership Recruitment Still Faulty" *The Guardian*, December 11.

Diamond, L. (2002). Free and Fair? The Administration and Conduct of The 1983 Nigerian Elections. In A. A. Idang, *Nigerian Government and Politics: (1979-1983)*. Calabar: Wusen Publishers.

Dode, O. (2010). Political Parties and The Prospect of Democratic Consolidation in Nigeria: 1999-2006. *African Journal of Political Science*, 4(5), 188-194.

Edigheji, O. (2006). Political Representation in Africa: Towards a Conceptual Framework. *African Development Journal*, 31(3), 2-15.

Ekundayo, J. (2016). Political Leadership Recruitment process and Governance in Nigeria. *A post-field thesis submitted to the Department of Political Science & Public Administration, Babcock University, Ilishan-Remo, Ogun State*.

Ezediumo Frances (2023) "Osun 2022 Election: Most monetized in State's History" *Daily Post*, July 18

Filipet, T. (2012). Political Leaders: The Paradox of Freedom and Democracy . *Departamento de Ciencias Sociais, Politicas e do Territorio Universidade de Aveiro*, 1(16), 113-131.

Gleeson Brent (2024) The Top 5 Leadership Trends that will Drive Success in 2024. *Forbes*. Retrieved from <https://www.forbes.com/sites/brentgleeson/2024/01/02/the-top-5-leadership-trends-that-will-drive-success-in-2024> .

Haslam Alexander, Alverson Mats and Reicher Stephen (2024) Leadership: Dead Ideas

Popoola Michael Akin and Arije Olaniyi Ezekiel

Advance Journal of Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences

Adv. J. Arts. Hum. & Soc Sci.

Volume: 8; Issue: 04

July-August, 2025

ISSN 6300-5290

E-ISSN 4226-6348

Impact Factor: 6.79

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/ajahss/index.php/ajahss/index>

- that still Work Among Us. The Leadership Quarterly (Elsevier) Vol.34, issue 3. Retrieved from <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1048984323000966>
- Havard Business School (2024) Developing Yourself as a Leader-Virtual. Retrieved from <https://www.exed.hbs.edu/developing-yourself-leader-virtual?>
- Hopkin, J. & Bradbury, C. (2006). British statewide parties and multilevel politics. *Oxford Journal of Social Science*, 36(1), 135-152.
- Ibrahim, J. (2007). Nigeria's 2007 Elections. The pitful path to Democracy Citizenship Special Report 182. *United States Institutes of Peace (USIP)* <http://www.usip.org>.
- Idada, W. and Uhumwuangho, S.O. (2012). Problems of Democratic Governance in Nigeria: The Way Forward. *Journal of Sociology and Anthropology*, 3(1), 49-54.
- Jinadu, L. (2011). *Inter-Party dialogue in Nigeria: Examining The Past, Present and Future*. Abuja: Political Parties dialogue series held at the Bolingo Hotels .
- Jinadu, A. (2011). Election Management Bodies in West Africa: A Comparative Studies of the Contribution of Electoral Commission to the Strengthening of Democracy. *Open society Initiative for West Africa*, 1(2), 1-25.
- Lamidi O., Oyeleke K., Fagbohun F., and Ihemeje G. (2014) "Exploring the character of Political Parties, Civil Society Organizations, security Agencies, Traditional Institutions and the Press in Nigeria Electoral Process" In *African Journal of Political science and International Relations*, 8(3), 54-80.
- Liden Robert, Wang Xing and Wang Yue (2025). The Evolution of Leadership: Past Insight, Present Trends and Future Direction. *Journal of Business Research*. (Elsevier) Vol.186, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.busres.2024.115036>
- Luqman, S. (2009). Electoral Institution and The Management of the Democratisation Process: The Nigerian Experience. *Journal of Social Sciences*, 21(1), 59-65.
- Masciulli, J. Molichanov, M.A & Knight, W.A . (2009). Political Leadership in Context. *The Ashgate Research Companion to Political Leadership*, 3(2), 127-139.
- Nwachukwu, J.O. (2022) Ekiti Decides 2022: Update Results from Governorship Election. *Daily Post*, June 18

Popoola Michael Akin and Arije Olaniyi Ezekiel

Advance Journal of Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences

Adv. J. Arts. Hum. & Soc Sci.

Volume: 8; Issue: 04

July-August, 2025

ISSN 6300-5290

E-ISSN 4226-6348

Impact Factor: 6.79

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/ajahss/index.php/ajahss/index>

Nwagboso, C. & Duke, O (2012). Nigeria and The Challenges of Leadership in the 21st Century: A Critique . *International Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, 2(3), 230-237.

Nwangwu Chikodiri (2015) Biometric Voting Technology and the 2015 General Elections in Nigeria. Being a Paper Presented at a Two-Day National Conference on “The 2015 General Elections in Nigeria: The Real Issues”. Organized by The Electoral Institute between 27th and 28th July 2015

Nye, J. (2008). *The Power to Lead*. New York: Oxford University Press.

Okoye, F. (2007). *Assessing The Credibility of Elections: The Challenges and The Problematic*. Abuja: Human Rights Monitor.

Olayinka Collins and Chibueze Joseph (2024). 129 Million Nigerians Living Below Poverty Lines_Says World Bank. *The Guardian*, October 18, 2024

Suberu R. (2007)" Nigeria's Muddled Elections" in *Journal of Democracy*, Vol.18, No 4.

Ukaegbu, C. (2010). Nigeria: Beyond Good Governance At 50. *IJARBSS*, 2(7), 185-191.

United Nations Development Programme (2024). Human Development Reports Retrieved from www.hdr.undp.org/en/2024-update

.World Economics (2025) Nigeria GDP \$2.593 Trillion in 2025. Retrieved from <https://www.worlddeconomics.com/process/Economics-countries-Gross-DomesticProduct.aspx?Country=Nigeria>